

Project identification

Please indicate whether the information refers to a multi-actor project or a thematic network

 Multi-actor project

Mandatory

Project Information

Project identifier

Title of the project in native language
(can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise repeat the title in English)

Title of the project in English (provide the project ACRONYM + short title within the characters limit)

Geographical location

Country (of the coordinator)

Main geographical location (NUTS3)
(of coordinator - for geolocalisation on map)

Editor of the text: person/organisation responsible for delivering the text

Project coordinator (lead-partner) according to the cooperation/consortium agreement:

Name	Stichting VU
Address	De boelelaan 1105, 1081 HV Amsterdam, Netherlands
E-mail	foodcllic.beta@vu.nl
Telephone	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31

Project period:

start year (YYYY)	2022
end year (YYYY)	2027

Project status: ongoing (after selection of the project) or completed (after final payment)

Main **funding source** (Rural development programme, H2020, or other EU, national/regional or private funds)

Total budget of the project (total costs - in euros)

11.418.499,30

Objective of the project in English: what problems/opportunities does the project address that are relevant for the practitioner/end-user, and how will they be solved? - (300-600 characters, word count – no spaces)

FoodCLIC strengthens science-policy-practice interfaces across and within European and African city-regions. In these city-regions, multi-stakeholder groups aim to transform food environments to make healthy and sustainable food available, affordable and attractive to all residents, including deprived and vulnerable groups. Through learning-in-action, FoodCLIC contributes to a policy-relevant evidence-base for sustainable food system transformation. Capacity building and direct support from FoodCLIC enable policy actors and urban planners to develop integrated urban food policies and render planning frameworks food sensitive.

Objective of the project in native language (can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise indicate "see objectives in English") (300-600 characters, word count – no spaces)

FoodCLIC strengthens science-policy-practice interfaces across and within European and African city-regions. In these city-regions, multi-stakeholder groups aim to transform food environments to make healthy and sustainable food available, affordable and attractive to all residents, including deprived and vulnerable groups. Through learning-in-action, FoodCLIC contributes to a policy-relevant evidence-base for sustainable food system transformation. Capacity building and direct support from FoodCLIC enable policy actors and urban planners to develop integrated urban food policies and render planning frameworks food sensitive.

Description of project activities in English: (max 600 characters, word count – no spaces): short summary highlighting main project activities.

All citizens should be able to fill their plate with nutritious, safe, sustainable and affordable food. However, Europe's urban areas are struggling to ensure availability and consumption of healthy, sustainable food for all. With this in mind, the EU-funded FoodCLIC project (<https://foodcllic.eu/>) supports the creation of sustainable urban food environments in European and African city-regions by strengthening multi-stakeholder Food Policy Networks that experiment with innovative approaches and business models in Living Labs. FoodCLIC supports multi-stakeholder engagement, also including deprived and vulnerable groups, making sure that all food system actors are heard and involved.

Description of project activities in native language: *(can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners)* (can be (max 600 characters, word count – no spaces): short summary highlighting main project activities.

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Description of the context of the project in English (e.g. drivers in legislation/ markets or other causes that were at the origin of the project, etc.)

Additional information on the project in English (as appropriate e.g. about activities to connect with the relevant sector and actors, farmers, businesses, etc.)

A large, empty rectangular box with a thin black border, intended for providing additional information about the project in English. The box is currently blank.

Additional comments (in English): free text field which can be used by the editor e.g. for listing facilitating elements or obstacles for the implementation of the produced results, for suggestions for future actions/research, for messages to end-users etc.

A large, empty rectangular box with a thin black border, intended for entering additional comments. It occupies the right two-thirds of the page width and extends from the top of the text area down to approximately the middle of the page.

Project partners

	Name	Address	E-mail	Telephone	Type of partner	Consent for publication
project coordinator (lead partner) from PROJECT INFORMATION	Stichting VU	De boelelaan 1105, 1081 HV Ar	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	research institute	yes
project partner	Aarhus Universitet	Agro Food Park 48, 8200, Aarhus, Denmark	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	research institute	yes
project partner	Area Metropolitana de Barcelona	Carrer 62 Num 16-18, 08040, Barcelona, Spain	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	other	yes
project partner	Budapest Fovaros Onkormanyzata	Varoshaz UTCA9-11, 1052, Budapest, Hungary	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	other	yes
project partner	Cariplo Factory SRL	Via Daniele Mann 23, 20121, Milan, Italy	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	SME	yes
project partner	Fondazione Centro Euro- Mediterraneosui Cambiamenti Climatici	via Marco Biagi 5 - 73100 Lecce, Italy	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31		yes
project partner	Comune di Capannori	Piazza Aldo Moro 1, 55012, Capannori, Italy	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	other	yes
project partner	EMAC Empresa Municipal de Ambientede Cascais EM SA	Complexo Municipal Multiservicios Da ADR, 2645138, Alcabideche, Portugal	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	SME	yes
project partner	ESSRG Nonprofit KFT	Ferenciek Tere 2 1 EM, Budapest, Hungary	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	research institute	yes
project partner	Ernährungsrat Berlin E.V.	IOW Postdamer Strasse 105, 10785, Berlin, Germany	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	other	yes
project partner	European Food Banks Federation	Chaussee de Louvain 775, 1140, Brussels, Belgium	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	other	yes
project partner	Faculdade de Medicina da Universidade de Lisboa	Avenida Professor Egas Moniz, 1649-028, Lisbon, Portugal	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	research institute	yes
project partner	Fundacio Provada Institut de Recerca de la Sida- Caixa	Carretera de Canyet, 08916, Barcelona, Spain	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	research institute	yes
project partner	Humboldt-Universitaet zu Berlin	Unter den Linden 6, 10099, Berlin, Germany	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	research institute	yes
project partner	ICLEI European Secretariat GMBH (ICLEI EUROPASEKRETARIAT GMBH)	Leopoldring 3, 79098, Freiburg im Breisgau, Germany	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	other	yes
project partner	ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability EV	Kaiser Friedrichstrasse 7, 53113, Bonn, Germany	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	other	yes
project partner	ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability - Africa	Knowledge Park III, Heron Crescent, Centu, 7441, Cape Town, South Africa	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	other	yes
project partner	Instituto de Ciências Sociais da Universidade de Lisboa	Av. Prof. Anibal de Bettencourt 9, 1600189, Lisbon, Portugal	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	research institute	yes
project partner	Municipiul Braşov	Bulevardul Eroilor 8, 500007, Brasov, Romania	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	other	yes
project partner	Stichting Voedsel Verbindt	De Boelelaan 1109, 1081 HV, Amsterdam, The Netherlands	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	other	yes
project partner	Universita di Pisa	Lungarno Pacinotti 43/44, 56126, Italy	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	research institute	yes
project partner	Universitatea Transilvania din Braşov	Bdul Eroilor 29, 500036, Brasov, Romania	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	research institute	yes
project partner	Aarhus Kommune	Radhuspladsen 2, 8100, Aarhus, Denmark	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	other	yes
project partner	Fondazione Centro Euro- Mediterraneosui Cambiamenti Climatici	Via a Imperatore 16, 73100, Lecce, Italy	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	research institute	yes
project partner	Association Mondiale des Grandes Metropoles	33 Rue Barbet de Jouy, 75007, Paris, France	foodclibeta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	other	yes

project partner	Gemeente Amsterdam	Amstel 1, 1011 PN, Amsterdam The Netherlands	foodclic.beta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	other	yes
project partner	Cardiff University	Newport Road 30-36, CF24 ODE, Cardiff, UK	foodclic.beta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	research institute	yes
project partner	University of Surrey	Guildford Surrey	foodclic.beta@vu.nl	+31 (0)20 - 598 70 31	research institute	yes

Keyword - category

food environments	Food quality / processing and nutrition
food policies	Food quality / processing and nutrition
planning frameworks	Food quality / processing and nutrition
science based and integr	Food quality / processing and nutrition
science-policy-practice in	Food quality / processing and nutrition
city-regions	Food quality / processing and nutrition
deprived and vulnerable g	Food quality / processing and nutrition
real-life interventions	Food quality / processing and nutrition
living labs	Food quality / processing and nutrition

Mandatory

Optional

Optional

Optional

Optional

Optional

Optional

Optional

Optional

Optional

Audiovisual material which is useful and attractive for practitioners (e.g. YouTube link, videos, other dissemination material)

Title/description (in English)	URL	Additional comments
The Farmer Miller Baker network in Buda	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aRV3InLL5pk	

Official website of the project

Title/description	URL	Additional comments
FoodCLIC project website	https://foodclic.eu/	

Links to other website(s) hosting information on the project (results) that are available after the project has ended, by preference using the existing local/regional/national communication channels that practitioners most often use.

Title/description	URL	Additional comments
integrated urban FOOD policies – developing sustainabilit	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060717	

Practice "abstract" 1:		
Short title in English	The Special Plan for Baix Llobregat near Barcelona	
<p>Short summary for practitioners in English on the <u>final or expected outcomes</u> (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). <i>Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English</i></p> <p>This summary should at least contain the following information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Main results/outcomes of the activity (expected or final) – The main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results? <p>This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a <u>direct and easy understandable language</u> and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.</p>	<p>As part of the FoodCLIC project (www.foodclic.eu), partners from the Barcelona Metropolitan Area mapped the importance of the Special Plan for the Protection and Improvement of the Baix Llobregat Agricultural Park (3,000 hectares in the delta and lower valley of the Llobregat River very close to Barcelona). It is a spatial planning tool aiming to safeguard and enhance natural and agricultural landscapes by implementing regulations and measures that restrict urbanisation within its territory, while maintaining a balance between agricultural, ecological, and social functions. The Plan has successfully curtailed urban pressure on the Park by prohibiting development, unless directly related to sustainable agriculture. Within the Park, ecological connectivity is promoted via cardio-healthy routes and recreational orchards, which create public health co-benefits.</p> <p>The governing Park Consortium facilitates participatory round table dialogues to improve collaboration between farmers, associations, and local authorities and to increase agricultural knowledge and support self-employed workers to access land. They also address issues of inclusive and fair land management by including marginalised farmers (i.e. young farmers and farm workers who are not landowners) in the oversight and use of the park. Ultimately, the Park and associated Special Plan serves as a catalyst for fostering a deeper connection and recognition of the cultural and historical significance of farming practices and communities.</p> <p>More information: https://www.amb.cat/en/web/amb/alimentacio/sistema-alimentari/produccio</p>	
Short title in native language	The Special Plan for Baix Llobregat near Barcelona	
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Practice "abstract" 2:			
Short title in English	Harmonising Local and Regional Policies for food system		
<p>Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). <i>Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English</i></p> <p>This summary should at least contain the following information: – Main results/outcomes of the activity (expected or final) – The main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?</p> <p>This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a <u>direct and easy understandable language</u>, and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.</p>	<p>As part of the FoodCLIC project, Romanian project partners highlighted the importance of the Flywheel Markets Framework in Brasov, as a proactive step towards establishing producers' fairs, and prioritising access to local, high-quality, fresh food. The framework fosters transparency and sustainable practices and actively involves farmers with organic certification, and local certification (to encourage short food chains). The market stalls in Brasov are marked with distinct colours for the direct producers (yellow), the resellers of agro-food products (blue), and the local agricultural producers from the Brasov mountainous areas (green).</p> <p>In parallel, the city-regional "Integrated Development Strategy of the Brasov Metropolitan Area," focuses on innovation, entrepreneurship, and human capital. It seeks to attract and support local production companies. The policy aims to improve society's health and actively supports local farmers. It establishes linkages between rural farmers and urban educational institutions, ensuring the provision of healthy food to schools and fostering knowledge sharing. This inclusive approach addresses the needs of various demographics, including low-income pensioners, single-parent families, students, and small farms.</p> <p>By meaningfully connecting rural and urban areas through policy institutions and action, farmers and consumers connect with each other, build trust, and add transparency to the food supply chain. Harmonising local and regional policies is crucial for reinforcing programming and generating co-benefits that positively impact the larger population. This alignment ensures a holistic approach to sustainable development,</p>		
Short title in native language	Harmonising Local and Regional Policies for food system transformation in Brasov, Romania		
<p>Short summary for practitioners in native language (can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).</p> <p>This summary should at least contain the following information: – Main results/outcomes of the activity (expected or final) – The main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?</p> <p>This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a <u>direct and easy understandable language</u>, and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.</p>	<p>As part of the FoodCLIC project, Romanian project partners highlighted the importance of the Flywheel Markets Framework in Brasov, as a proactive step towards establishing producers' fairs, and prioritising access to local, high-quality, fresh food. The framework fosters transparency and sustainable practices and actively involves farmers with organic certification, and local certification (to encourage short food chains). The market stalls in Brasov are marked with distinct colours for the direct producers (yellow), the resellers of agro-food products (blue), and the local agricultural producers from the Brasov mountainous areas (green).</p> <p>In parallel, the city-regional "Integrated Development Strategy of the Brasov Metropolitan Area," focuses on innovation, entrepreneurship, and human capital. It seeks to attract and support local production companies. The policy aims to improve society's health and actively supports local farmers. It establishes linkages between rural farmers and urban educational institutions, ensuring the provision of healthy food to schools and fostering knowledge sharing. This inclusive approach addresses the needs of various demographics, including low-income pensioners, single-parent families, students, and small farms.</p> <p>By meaningfully connecting rural and urban areas through policy institutions and action, farmers and consumers connect with each other, build trust, and add transparency to the food supply chain. Harmonising local and regional policies is crucial for reinforcing programming and generating co-benefits that positively impact the larger population. This alignment ensures a holistic approach to sustainable development, emphasising the well-being of the community.</p>		

Practice "abstract" 3:			
Short title in English	How Budapest strengthens its local food system through its national		
<p>Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). <i>Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English</i></p> <p>This summary should at least contain the following information: – Main results/outcomes of the activity (expected or final) – The main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?</p> <p>This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using <u>a direct and easy understandable language</u>, and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.</p>	<p>As part of the FoodCLIC project (www.foodclic.eu), the Budapest city-region sheds light on how national legislations can support local food systems. In 2020, in order to protect local small farmers, the Hungarian Chamber of Agriculture (a public body, representing farmers' interests) issued a national law that establishes a legal category for small-scale farmers who are entitled to have a special licence to sell their products at food markets under favourable tax conditions. Despite this regulation, farmers suffer from unfair competition with "pseudo farmers" who do not produce the food, but act as distributors and sell it at local markets. They only own a small plot of land and pretend to receive the same benefits as true small-scale producers even if they sell lower quality and cheaper food bought from wholesale markets. In response, a new legislation aims to create an open online dataset where true small-scale farmers are registered and all consumers can check the origin of produce by scanning a QR code, using an app or a web page. This national law is particularly relevant in Budapest where the presence of the pseudo farmers reached over two-thirds at the food markets.</p> <p>The city governance further aims to strengthen the position of local smallholder farmers through advocating for the adoption of short supply chains (next to other relevant issues, such as: food waste reduction, food safety and security, and the promotion of urban agriculture); to be incorporated in the Long Term Urban Development Concept, which is expected to be applied no later than June 2025. Furthermore, this endeavour will be supported through the Climate City Contract in relation to the 100 Net Zero cities initiative, and the new SECAP of the city.</p>		
Short title in native language	How Budapest strengthens its local food system through its national		69 character(s) / 150
<p>Short summary for practitioners in native language (can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).</p> <p>This summary should at least contain the following information: – Main results/outcomes of the activity (expected or final) – The main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?</p> <p>This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using <u>a direct and easy understandable language</u>, and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.</p>	<p>As part of the FoodCLIC project (www.foodclic.eu), the Budapest city-region sheds light on how national legislations can support local food systems. In 2020, in order to protect local small farmers, the Hungarian Chamber of Agriculture (a public body, representing farmers' interests) issued a national law that establishes a legal category for small-scale farmers who are entitled to have a special licence to sell their products at food markets under favourable tax conditions. Despite this regulation, farmers suffer from unfair competition with "pseudo farmers" who do not produce the food, but act as distributors and sell it at local markets. They only own a small plot of land and pretend to receive the same benefits as true small-scale producers even if they sell lower quality and cheaper food bought from wholesale markets. In response, a new legislation aims to create an open online dataset where true small-scale farmers are registered and all consumers can check the origin of produce by scanning a QR code, using an app or a web page. This national law is particularly relevant in Budapest where the presence of the pseudo farmers reached over two-thirds at the food markets.</p> <p>The city governance further aims to strengthen the position of local smallholder farmers through advocating for the adoption of short supply chains (next to other relevant issues, such as: food waste reduction, food safety and security, and the promotion of urban agriculture); to be incorporated in the Long Term Urban Development Concept, which is expected to be applied no later than June 2025. Furthermore, this endeavour will be supported through the Climate City Contract in relation to the 100 Net Zero cities initiative, and the new SECAP of the city.</p>		1472 character(s) / 1500

Practice "abstract" 4:		
Short title in English	How municipalities in the Plain of Lucca are transforming their city-	
<p>Short summary for practitioners in English on the <u>final or expected outcomes</u> (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). <i>Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English</i></p> <p>This summary should at least contain the following information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Main results/outcomes of the activity (expected or final) – The main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results? <p>This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a <u>direct and easy understandable language</u> and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.</p>	<p>In 2018, in the Plain of Lucca, a participatory process led four municipalities - Capannori, Altopascio, Porcari and Villa Basilica – to design a common food strategy to develop local, sustainable and just food systems. “Piana del Cibo” (https://pianadelcibo.it/) is the territorial food strategy that contains guiding principles, goals and actionable measures co-designed by these municipalities and more than 300 local stakeholders involved in the overall process.</p> <p>Based on the Food Strategy, a dedicated governance structure has been designed, composed of several entities, ranging from the Food Policy Office to the thematic Working Tables of the Agorà. The latter is an open assembly, representing the diversity of local food stakeholders and contributing to decision-making on food matters. These entities collaborate for the purpose of designing local policies in a coherent and integrated manner.</p> <p>To date, the Piana del Cibo has undertaken various initiatives aimed at enhancing food education and raising awareness, promoting sustainable local food production, and implementing projects to improve access to nutritious food for recipients of food assistance. Although these efforts have been constrained by the challenges posed by the pandemic, the initiative is currently in the process of reassessing and revitalising its endeavours. As part of the EU-funded FoodCLIC project (www.foodclic.eu), the municipalities will continue to build on these measures to promote food systems transformation, with a focus on food education, access to good and sustainable food for all, and local food supply chains.</p>	
Short title in native language	How municipalities in the Plain of Lucca are transforming their city-	
<p>Short summary for practitioners in native language (<i>can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English</i>) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).</p> <p>This summary should at least contain the following information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Main results/outcomes of the activity (expected or final) – The main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results? <p>This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a <u>direct and easy understandable language</u> and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.</p>	<p>In 2018, in the Plain of Lucca, a participatory process led four municipalities - Capannori, Altopascio, Porcari and Villa Basilica – to design a common food strategy to develop local, sustainable and just food systems. “Piana del Cibo” (https://pianadelcibo.it/) is the territorial food strategy that contains guiding principles, goals and actionable measures co-designed by these municipalities and more than 300 local stakeholders involved in the overall process.</p> <p>Based on the Food Strategy, a dedicated governance structure has been designed, composed of several entities, ranging from the Food Policy Office to the thematic Working Tables of the Agorà. The latter is an open assembly, representing the diversity of local food stakeholders and contributing to decision-making on food matters. These entities collaborate for the purpose of designing local policies in a coherent and integrated manner.</p> <p>To date, the Piana del Cibo has undertaken various initiatives aimed at enhancing food education and raising awareness, promoting sustainable local food production, and implementing projects to improve access to nutritious food for recipients of food assistance. Although these efforts have been constrained by the challenges posed by the pandemic, the initiative is currently in the process of reassessing and revitalising its endeavours. As part of the EU-funded FoodCLIC project (www.foodclic.eu), the municipalities will continue to build on these measures to promote food systems transformation, with a focus on food education, access to good and sustainable food for all, and local food supply chains.</p>	

Practice "abstract" 5:		
Short title in English	Creating synergies between FoodCLIC and the Climate Action Plan in	
<p>Short summary for practitioners in English on the <u>final or expected outcomes</u> (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). <i>Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English</i></p> <p>This summary should at least contain the following information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Main results/outcomes of the activity (expected or final) – The main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results? <p>This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a <u>direct and easy understandable language</u> and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.</p>	<p>influences and guides policies and priorities with the municipal area. It extends to encompass activities engaging the business community in Aarhus and its residents. The Climate Strategy 2030 and an associated Climate Action Plan 2021-2024 operationalize the efforts towards this goal.</p> <p>Aarhus aims to achieve a climate-friendly, more localized food production. The municipality supports a green transition through new “business models, technologies and value chain collaborations”. Accordingly, the Climate Action Plan promotes changes in land-use and agricultural practices, implementing a green food procurement strategy in canteens operated by the municipality including increased purchase of organic produce and the implementation of an internal CO2 tax on specific products like red meat.</p> <p>During the development of the Climate Action Plan 2025-2030, the FoodCLIC project has been instrumental in bringing a more holistic approach to transforming food systems to the table. For example, by considering all the components of the CLIC conceptual framework in the policy discussions and including it at the heart of co-creation activities with relevant stakeholders: To ensure Co-benefits, the conservation of biodiversity is addressed. Local food production initiatives foster rural-urban Linkages. The collaborative work encourages Connectivities between public-private sectors, promoting green growth, green transition skills, and technology implementation. And to secure Inclusion, access and awareness regarding healthier food is promoted.</p>	
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Practice "abstract" 6:		
Short title in English	Berlin food hubs as centres of life ("LebensMittelPunkte")	
<p>Short summary for practitioners in English on the <u>final or expected outcomes</u> (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). <i>Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English</i></p> <p>This summary should at least contain the following information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Main results/outcomes of the activity (expected or final) – The main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results? <p>This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a <u>direct and easy understandable language</u> and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.</p>	<p>The "Netzwerk der LebensmittelPunkte" (LMPs) (English: ~ network of food hubs), which was launched in Berlin (https://lebensmittelpunkte-berlin.de/), is an open network of local projects, neighbourhood communities, organisations and committed individuals. The food hubs (LMPs) are innovative meeting/ community spaces that are intended to help overcome structural and knowledge barriers within the neighbourhoods and between consumers and food producers. The shared vision of all members is to create LMPs, i.e. food hubs and so-called centres of life, in every neighbourhood for an ecological and socially just food transition in Berlin.</p> <p>One example is "Das Baumhaus" (https://lebensmittelpunkte-berlin.de/baumhaus/), a creative community space that serves as a weekly collection point for organic fruit and vegetable boxes from community-supported agriculture, offers community meals, community cooking and engages the neighbourhood in food transition workshops. Many hubs also serve as a distribution hub for food-sharing and food rescue initiatives and raise awareness on food transition and local food processing and supply. "Das Baumhaus" also serves as the LMP network hub and has received city funding to help co-ordinate the growing network.</p> <p>LMPs are either fully set-up and run by volunteers or hosted by a community centre or library and supported by volunteers. The network co-ordination team can support individual hubs by offering practical advice and trainings, such as on food hygiene. Currently, the network hosts around 30 hubs in Berlin.</p>	
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Practice "abstract" 7:	
Short title in English	Making organic food accessible to all - the good practice case of
<p>Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). <i>Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English</i></p> <p>This summary should at least contain the following information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Main results/outcomes of the activity (expected or final) – The main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results? <p>This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using <u>a direct and easy understandable language</u> and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.</p>	<p>Aligned with the Food Transition Strategy of the Lisbon Metropolitan Area, the municipality of Cascais is now developing a local sustainable food strategy programme - Terras de Cascais (English: ~ Land of Cascais) – that is managed by Empresa Municipal de Ambiente de Cascais (https://ambiente.cascais.pt/pt/terrasdecascais/terras-cascais). The programme is based on the idea that local, seasonal, and organic food should be accessible to all, and aims to promote and support a sustainable agricultural production system on public and private lands in Cascais. Since 2009 the concept has proven to be successful among people either wanting to produce their own food, returning to their farming roots, or just wanting to reduce their monthly expenses.</p> <p>The initiative centres around community garden projects, which actively involve residents in decision-making processes in the Cascais municipality. Through its implementation, it has achieved remarkable outcomes across various sustainability dimensions. As of 2021, Terras de Cascais comprised 29 community vegetable gardens, 3 community vineyards, and 2 community orchards, totalling up to 631 families cultivating a piece of land in a sustainable way.</p> <p>Among these plots of land, Terras de Cascais owns a very popular vegetable garden at Quinta do Pisão, where residents of Cascais can pick and buy fresh vegetables: Quinta do Pisão is a 380 ha nature park that was redeveloped by Cascais City Council. This garden exists because of a multi-organisational partnership that came together to protect valuable land and support long-term unemployed people in learning new skills. Schools and other groups can visit the garden for</p>
Short title in native language	Making organic food accessible to all - the good practice case of

<p>Short summary for practitioners in <u>native language</u> (<i>can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English</i>) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).</p> <p>This summary should at least contain the following information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Main results/outcomes of the activity (expected or final) – The main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results? <p>This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using <u>a direct and easy understandable language</u> and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.</p>	<p>Aligned with the Food Transition Strategy of the Lisbon Metropolitan Area, the municipality of Cascais is now developing a local sustainable food strategy programme - Terras de Cascais (English: ~ Land of Cascais) – that is managed by Empresa Municipal de Ambiente de Cascais (https://ambiente.cascais.pt/pt/terrasdecascais/terras-cascais). The programme is based on the idea that local, seasonal, and organic food should be accessible to all, and aims to promote and support a sustainable agricultural production system on public and private lands in Cascais. Since 2009 the concept has proven to be successful among people either wanting to produce their own food, returning to their farming roots, or just wanting to reduce their monthly expenses.</p> <p>The initiative centres around community garden projects, which actively involve residents in decision-making processes in the Cascais municipality. Through its implementation, it has achieved remarkable outcomes across various sustainability dimensions. As of 2021, Terras de Cascais comprised 29 community vegetable gardens, 3 community vineyards, and 2 community orchards, totalling up to 631 families cultivating a piece of land in a sustainable way.</p> <p>Among these plots of land, Terras de Cascais owns a very popular vegetable garden at Quinta do Pisão, where residents of Cascais can pick and buy fresh vegetables: Quinta do Pisão is a 380 ha nature park that was redeveloped by Cascais City Council. This garden exists because of a multi-organisational partnership that came together to protect valuable land and support long-term unemployed people in learning new skills. Schools and other groups can visit the garden for educational purposes and participate in training for gardeners and non-</p>
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Practice "abstract" 8:		
Short title in English	The Amsterdam Metropolitan Area Pursues Sustainability from Soil to	
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Practice "abstract" 9:		
Short title in English	The Role of Food Policy Networks in Berlin	
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Practice "abstract" 10:		
Short title in English	How local government officials can overcome barriers to support	
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